

CORRUPTION IS A FACTOR THAT DESTROYS OUR SOCIETY

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Corruption as a social phenomenon has been known since ancient times, since the establishment of the institution of power and social division on this basis. Unfortunately, often people who are entrusted with public administration believe that their financial situation should be constantly improved, and corruption is the ideal mechanism for this. As a result, this leads to massive facts of corruption in the state and in society, and if the state apparatus does not fight this problem. Since it is completely "rotten" from the inside, then the state is destroyed either through revolutions or by capture by another state, in connection with which there is a significant "step back" in the development of the country or its complete destruction.

Corruption is a large-scale social phenomenon that reflects such processes in the state as the decomposition of power, the use of official positions by state representatives for the purpose of personal, individual or group, material financial enrichment.

From a psychological point of view, a person perceives the concept of justice biased. In the event that someone was able to achieve his or her own goals with the help of bribery, this fact is considered injustice. However, if he achieved the same goal with the assistance of the same corruption tool, then this fact was defined as fair. That is, corruption is a beneficial measure for each subject of the issue under consideration. The phenomenon of corruption accompanies Uzbekistan history throughout its existence and development. Any law aimed at reducing corruption is met with opposition from society, since this feature is a national character, and bribery itself is part of the Russian mentality. Sociologists believe that corruption in the minds of the Russian population is perceived at a legitimate level and is not associated with something immoral and illegal [2].

The main problems caused by corruption are the inhibition of economic and social transformations, the expansion of the shadow economy, the reduction of tax amounts to the treasury, and the irrational unproductive distribution of public funds. Corruption also leads to the formation of a negative image of the country, which, in turn, leads to a deterioration in the investment climate in the state. Moreover, corruption is a solid platform for the development of crime, terrorist and extremist manifestations in the country. Corruption is the wrong

side of society, characterizing and aggravating its moral decline and degradation [1].

It is necessary to identify further the causes and main factors of corruption:

- ✓ the rapid ill-conceived transition to market relations against the backdrop of world globalization;
- ✓ unjustified privatization, carried out with a huge number of offenses, as a result of which an insignificant part of the new owners turned out to be the winners;
- ✓ low management efficiency (incompleteness and imperfection of the administrative reform);
- ✓ flaws in legislation and its lagging behind the development of socio-economic relations;
- ✓ lack of elementary legal literacy, knowledge of laws on the part of society;
- ✓ personnel technical and operational unpreparedness of law enforcement agencies to counter organized crime, including corrupt structures at all levels of government;
- ✓ lack of developed institutions of civil society [3].

The fundamental tool for suppressing corruption schemes and activities is the legal system, which is a kind of barrier to the implementation of corrupt transactions between government officials and the population of the country. This legal system is based on an independent anti-corruption expertise of draft laws, the task of which is to identify the most typical and formalized manifestations of corruption in the text of adopted laws, containing clear legal definitions, excluding ambiguous wording, having a conceptual apparatus characteristic of the domestic legal system, not containing conflict of laws rules, as well as an excessive number of reference norms, the presence of which is unacceptable on the most fundamental issues of combating corruption [2]. However, this expertise is not a sufficient measure to reduce the level of corruption in Uzbekistan. The main message and impetus for the development of corruption is produced due to excessive administration by the state, which in turn slows down the processes of social formation and increasing the efficiency of the national economy. Corruption as a deterministic phenomenon on the part of state bodies creates a certain high degree of anxiety and distrust of the authorities on the part of society, forming a negative image of the country in the international space.

The paradox in the context of this topic lies in the fact that corruption will not be eradicated if the citizens of the state themselves do not oppose it, and generate,

become its source. Those measures that are currently aimed at the fight against corruption by the state - anti-corruption committees, national projects, will continue to be ineffective against the backdrop of a latent positive attitude towards bribery on the part of society. To date, statistics show that the area most prone to corruption is healthcare and the education system. Thus, the most vulnerable areas turned out to be those that are directly responsible for the health and life of a person, and his formation as a person [4].

Corruption flourishes in those areas where there is the greatest contact between people, every person goes to clinics and hospitals, from an early age students are taught that it is possible to solve the problem by giving a bribe. This phenomenon determines another acute problem - the lack of competent specialists and professionals. On the part of government officials, corrupt transactions are determined due to low salaries, often the absence of a social package, and non-equivalence of wages. That is, bribery is a way of additional income and a decent existence, satisfaction of social, material needs.

Corruption is eradicated only under the condition of general consolidation, interaction of all parties, including state institutions, the citizens themselves. Among the main strategies for combating corruption should be a strategy for eliminating the conditions for corruption, which, in general, is not limited to a corrupt official, but is focused on eliminating incentives to commit corruption crimes.

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